

DEMPFIRLASH HADIGA EGA BO'LGAN DIFFUZIYA JARAYONINI SONLI
YECHIMINI GRAFIK KO'RINISHI

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Abstract. In this paper, the Cauchy problem for the $N=1$ case is numerically solved for the diffusion process described by the parabolic-type equation described by the convective migration and the damping term. The mesh is constructed through an iterative method and an undisclosed scheme. Through this numerical solution, he described the diffusion process graphically. The diffusion process can be used to describe most of the processes in nature, including biological population, pollution, and heat dissipation processes.

Keywords: Key words: damping term, numerical parameters, iteration method, algebraic equations, numerical solution, driving method, nonlinear diffusion process.

Anotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada konvektiv ko'chish va dempfirlash hadi orqali tasvirlanuvchi parabolik tipdagi tenglama bilan tasvirlangan diffuziya jarayoni uchun Koshi masalasi $N=1$ holatda sonli yechilgan. Iteratsiya usuli va oshkormas sxemasi orqali to'r qurilgan. Ushbu sonli yechim orqali diffuziya jarayonini grafik ko'rinishda tasvirlab bergan. Diffuziya jarayoni esa tabiatdagi aksariyat jarayonlarni jumladan biologik populyatsiya, ifloslanish, issiqlik tarqalish jarayonlarini tasvirlash mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: dempfirlash hadi, konvektiv ko'chish, sonli parametrlar, iteratsiya usuli, algebraik tenglamalar, sonli yechim, haydash usuli, chiziqli bo'lmagan diffuziya jarayoni.

Аннотация. В данной работе численно решается задача Коши для случая $N=1$ для диффузионного процесса, описываемого уравнением параболического типа, описываемым конвективной миграцией и членом затухания. Сетка строится с помощью итеративного метода и нераскрытой схемы. С помощью этого численного решения он графически описал процесс диффузии. Процесс диффузии можно использовать для описания большинства процессов в природе, включая биологическое заселение, загрязнение и процессы рассеивания тепла.

Ключевые слова: демпфирование давай, конвективная миграция, численные параметры, итерационный метод, алгебраические уравнения, численное решение, метод движения, нелинейный диффузионный процесс.

Quyidagi parabolik tipdagi nochiziqli tenglama uchun qo'yilgan Koshi masalasini ko'rib chiqamiz

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left| \frac{\partial u^{k_1}}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial u^{m_1}}{\partial x} \right) \pm s(t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - b_1 u^{q_1} \left| \frac{\partial v^{m_1}}{\partial x} \right|^{p_1} \quad (1)$$

(1) masalani sonli yechish uchun boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlar va nochiziqli tenglama uchun chekli ayirmalar sxemasini qurib olinadi (bir o'lchovli holda). Buning uchun [108; C. 556-560] t va x bo'yicha bir xil to'r quramiz

$$\overline{w_m} = \left\{ t_j = j\tau, j = 0, 1, \dots, m, m\tau = T; x_i = a + ih, i = 0, 1, \dots, n, h = \frac{b-a}{n} \right\}.$$

Oshkormas sxema asosida chekli ayirmalar sxemasi quriladi. Buning uchun balans usuli va oshkormas sxemasidan foydalanamiz

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{y_i^{j+1} - y_i^j}{\tau} &= \frac{1}{h^2} (a_{i+1} (y_{i+1}^{j+1} - y_i^{j+1}) - a_i (y_i^{j+1} - y_{i-1}^{j+1})) - v_i^{j+1} \frac{y_{i+1}^{j+1} - y_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2h} - \\ &- (y_i^{j+1})^{q_1} \left(\frac{(y^m)_{i+1}^{j+1} - (y^m)_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2h} \right)^{p_1}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1; j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1; \\ y_i^0 &= u_0(x_i), \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n; \\ y_0^j &= \phi_1(t_j), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m; \\ y_n^j &= \phi_2(t_j), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m. \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

bu yerda a_{i+1} va a_i - (1.1.1) masalaning nochiziqli hadlari. a_{i+1} va a_i quyidagi formulalar bilan aniqlanadi [108; C. 556-560]:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{i+1} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(y_i^{j+1})^{m-1} \left| \frac{(y_{i+1}^{j+1})^k - (y_i^{j+1})^k}{h} \right|^{p-2} + (y_{i+1}^{j+1})^{m-1} \left| \frac{(y_i^{j+1})^k - (y_{i-1}^{j+1})^k}{h} \right|^{p-2} \right], \\ a_i &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(y_{i-1}^{j+1})^{m-1} \left| \frac{(y_i^{j+1})^k - (y_{i-1}^{j+1})^k}{h} \right|^{p-2} + (y_i^{j+1})^{m-1} \left| \frac{(y_{i-1}^{j+1})^k - (y_{i-2}^{j+1})^k}{h} \right|^{p-2} \right], \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

$i = 1$ da a_i sohadan tashqariga chiqadi, bu holda quyidagi formuladan foydalanamiz: [13; 205-217]

$$\left. \frac{du}{dx} \right|_0 \approx \frac{-y_2 + 4y_1 - 3y_0}{2h} \tag{4}$$

yoki

$$\left. \frac{du}{dx} \right|_n \approx \frac{3y_n - 4y_{n-1} + y_{n-2}}{2h}. \tag{5}$$

(1.4.1) algebraik tenglamalar u^{j+1} ga nisbatan chiziqli bo'lmagan. Ushbu tenglamalarni sonli yechish uchun iterativ usullar qo'llaniladi. Biz ular uchun oddiy iteratsiya usulidan foydalanamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{y_i^{s+1j+1} - y_i^j}{\tau} &= \frac{1}{h^2} (a_{i+1} (y_{i+1}^{s+1j+1}) (y_{i+1}^{s+1j+1} - y_i^{s+1j+1}) - a_i (y_i^{s+1j+1}) (y_i^{s+1j+1} - y_{i-1}^{s+1j+1})) - v_i^{j+1} \frac{y_{i+1}^{s+1j+1} - y_{i-1}^{s+1j+1}}{2h} - \\ &- (y_i^{s+1j+1})^{q_1} \left(\frac{(y^m)_{i+1}^{j+1} - (y^m)_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2h} \right)^{p_1} \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

bu yerda $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Iteratsion sxema hisoblashda quyidagi shart asosida aniqlik belgilanadi va jarayon shu shart bajarilguncha davom etadi:

$$\max_{0 \leq i \leq n} \left| y_i^{s+1} - y_i^s \right| < \varepsilon$$

(1.1.1) masalani sonli yechishda iteratsiya jarayoni uchun $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$ deb olingan.

$y^j = y$, $y^{j+1} = \bar{y}$ almashtirish amalga oshirilib (1.4.5) ni quyidagi ko‘rinishda yozib olish mumkin

$$A_i^s y_{i-1}^{s+1} - C_i^s y_i^{s+1} + B_i^s y_{i+1}^{s+1} = -F_i^s, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1. \quad (7)$$

$$y_0 = \chi_1 y_1 + \mu_1,$$

$$y_N = \chi_2 y_{N-1} + \mu_2,$$

bu yerda haydash usuli koeffisientlari

$$A_i^s = \frac{\tau^s}{h^2} a_i + \frac{\tau^s}{2h} v_i^{j+1}, \quad B_i^s = \frac{\tau^s}{h^2} a_{i+1} - \frac{\tau^s}{2h} v_i^{j+1}, \quad C_i^s = A_i^s + B_{i+1}^s$$

$$F_i^s = y_i - (y_i^{j+1})^{q_1} \left(\frac{(y^m)_{i+1}^{j+1} - (y^m)_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2h} \right)^{p_1} \tau^s,$$

$$v(t) = 1/(T+t)^n \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ ga teng.}$$

Algebraik tenglamalar sistemasini (1.4.6) sonli yechish uchun haydash usuli qo‘llaniladi.

Usuliga ko‘ra

$$\bar{y}_i = \alpha_i \bar{y}_{i+1} + \beta_i \quad (8)$$

α_i, β_i - koeffisientlar quyidagicha aniqlanadi

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_{i+1} = \frac{B_i}{C_i - \alpha_i A_i}; \\ \beta_{i+1} = \frac{A_i \beta_i + F_i}{C_i - \alpha_i A_i}; \end{cases}$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

α_0, β_0 qiymatlari chegaraviy qiymatlar orqali aniqlanadi.

Haydash usulini qo‘llash uchun yetarli shart bajarilishi yetarli

$$A_i \neq 0, B_i \neq 0, |A_i| + |B_i| \leq C_i.$$

Konvektiv ko‘chishga ega bo‘lgan va dempirlash ta‘sirida ikki karra nochiziqli diffuziya tenglamani $Q = \{(t, x) : t > 0, x \in R\}$ da qaraymiz.

U ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p1 = 1.2
 p = 2.2
 m1 = 2.4
 k1 = 2
 b1 = 1.5
 q1 = 1.7

V ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p2 = 1.2
 p = 2.2
 m2 = 2.4
 k2 = 2
 b2 = 1.5
 q2 = 1.7

Animatsiya Grafik

Calculate

Ushbu ikkita konsentratsiyani vaqtning har bir onida parametrlarning turli qiymatlarida grafik ko'rinishlari quyidagi 1.4.1-1.4.7 rasmlarda tasvirlangan. **1-rasm.** $p1=1.2$, $p=2.2$, $m1=2.4$, $k1=2$, $b1=2.5$, $q1=1.7$, $p2=1.2$, $p=2.2$, $m2=2.4$, $k2=2$, $b2=1.5$, $q2=1.7$ qiymatlarda u va v konsentratsiyaning diffuziya jarayoni $t=0.6$ da.

2-rasm. $p1=1.2$, $p=2.2$, $m1=1.6$, $k1=1.5$, $b1=1.2$, $q1=1.5$, $p2=1.2$, $p=2.2$, $m2=1.6$, $k2=1.5$,

U ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p1 = 1.2
 p = 2.2
 m1 = 1.6
 k1 = 1.5
 b1 = 1.2
 q1 = 1.5

V ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p2 = 1.2
 p = 2.2
 m2 = 1.6
 k2 = 1.5
 b2 = 1.2
 q2 = 1.5

Animatsiya Grafik

Calculate

$b2=1.2$, $q2=1.5$ qiymatlarda u va v konsentratsiyaning diffuziya jarayoni $t=0.8$ da.

U ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p1 = 1.2
 p = 2.2
 m1 = 1.9
 k1 = 1.5
 b1 = 2.2
 q1 = 1.5

V ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p2 = 1.2
 p = 2.2
 m2 = 1.9
 k2 = 1.5
 b2 = 2.2
 q2 = 1.5

Animatsiya Grafik

Calculate

3-rasm. $p1=1.2, p=2.2, m1=1.9, k1=1.5, b1=2.2, q1=1.5, p2=1.2, p=2.2, m2=1.9, k2=1.5, b2=2.2, q2=1.5$ qiymatlarda u va v konsentratsiyaning diffuziya jarayoni $t=0.7$ da.

U ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p1 = 1.2
 p = 2.2
 m1 = 2.4
 k1 = 2
 b1 = 1.5
 q1 = 1.7

V ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p2 = 1.2
 p = 2.2
 m2 = 2.4
 k2 = 2
 b2 = 1.5
 q2 = 1.7

Animatsiya Grafik

Calculate

4-rasm. $p1=1.2, p=2.2, m1=2.4, k1=2, b1=1.5, q1=1.7, p2=1.2, p=2.2, m2=2.4, k2=2, b2=1.5, q2=1.7$ qiymatlarda u va v konsentratsiyaning diffuziya jarayoni $t=0.6$ da.

U ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p1 = 1.2
p = 2.2
m1 = 2.4
k1 = 2
b1 = 1.5
q1 = 1.7

V ni konsentratsiya parametrlar qiymatlarini kiriting:

p2 = 1.2
p = 2.2
m2 = 2.4
k2 = 2
b2 = 1.5
q2 = 1.7

Animatsiya

Grafik

Calculate

5-rasm. $p1=1.2$, $p=2.2$, $m1=2.4$, $k1=2$, $b1=1.5$, $q1=1.7$, $p2=1.2$, $p=2.2$, $m2=2.4$, $k2=2$, $b2=1.5$, $q2=1.7$ qiymatlarda u va v konsentratsiyaning diffuziya jarayoni $t=0.3$ da.

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